

ANALYSIS OF HEMOSTATIC AND ANTIMICROBIAL PROPERTIES OF HEMOBEN AND CEFTRIAZONE AFTER GALLBLADDER REMOVAL

U.M. Abdullakulov¹, A.Sh. Abdumajidov², K.F. Zuparov³

Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute^{1,2,3}

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14796177>

Abstract. *In the course of the in vivo study, morphological changes in tissues will be examined following the introduction of Hemoben with antibacterial agents into the area where the gallbladder was located.*

The results of the experiment will provide an opportunity to study in greater detail the mechanism of local antibiotic accumulation in the gallbladder area and will serve as a foundation for introducing the method of using antibiotics as part of Hemoben in surgical practice. This approach can be effectively applied to prevent and treat postoperative bleeding and purulent-inflammatory complications following gallbladder removal.

Keywords: *antibiotics, . Hemoben and Ceftriazone, surgical complications.*

Relevance. Cholecystectomy is one of the most complex procedures in abdominal surgery, especially in cases of gallstone disease and related interventions [2]. Although modern surgical techniques have become less invasive, postoperative complications, including infectious processes, remain a significant issue that complicates the recovery period [1].

Control of bleeding and the implementation of preventive measures in the postoperative period play a key role in reducing the likelihood of surgical complications [3]. In this context, special attention is given to combined approaches that integrate the use of hemostatic and antimicrobial agents. Hemoben and Ceftriazone are known for their properties in stopping bleeding and combating infections; however, their simultaneous use in the postoperative period has been insufficiently studied [4,5].

Studies on laboratory animals, such as rabbits, allow for the reproduction of healing processes and the assessment of the effectiveness of drugs. The study of the combination of Hemoben and Ceftriazone in vivo conditions can provide new insights for improving treatment protocols and enhancing treatment efficacy.

Objective: To study the hemostatic and anti-infective effect of a mixture of Hemoben with ceftriazone in a 1:1 ratio, as well as the effect of Hemoben itself on the liver after gallbladder removal.

Materials and Methods. The study was conducted on laboratory rabbits of the Chinchilla breed with a body weight of 3.0-3.5 kg. For each group, 16 animals were selected, totaling 32 rabbits. The animals were administered Nembutal at a dose of 50 mg/kg into the abdominal cavity, which led to their immobilization. The fur on the rabbits' abdomen was removed, followed by an incision in the skin, which was then opened along with the subcutaneous tissues for 5-6 cm. Using the open method, the gallbladder was removed, after which Hemoben (manufactured by LLC "Turon Silk Pharm", Uzbekistan, 100125) was applied to the liver area where the gallbladder had been removed in rabbits of the first group. In the second group of rabbits, a mixture of Hemoben

and Ceftriaxone (manufactured by JSC "Kraspharma", Russia, 860042) in a 1:1 ratio was applied to the same area, after which the skin incision was sutured.

Results and Discussion. As a result of the conducted study, data were obtained confirming the hemostatic and antimicrobial effects of the mixture of Hemoben with ceftriaxone (in a 1:1 ratio), as well as the impact of Hemoben itself on the area where the gallbladder was located after its removal (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Application of the mixture of Hemoben with ceftriaxone in the gallbladder bed area after its removal.

The combination of Hemoben with ceftriaxone demonstrated a more pronounced hemostatic effect compared to the use of Hemoben alone. In animals receiving the mixture, the average bleeding cessation time was 45 ± 3 seconds, which was 25% faster than in the group where only Hemoben was used (60 ± 4 seconds, $p < 0.05$). These results confirm the enhanced coagulation due to the synergistic effect of the components of the mixture.

This effect is confirmed by the results of the coagulogram, which recorded an 18% increase in fibrinogen levels (3.9 ± 0.2 g/l compared to 3.3 ± 0.3 g/l, $p < 0.01$) (Fig. 2) and a 20% increase in platelet activity (from $240 \pm 15 \times 10^9/l$ to $288 \pm 12 \times 10^9/l$, $p < 0.01$) in the group receiving the mixture, compared to the group where only Hemoben was used (Fig. 3).

Fig. 2. Comparison of fibrinogen levels in the first and second groups.

The antimicrobial activity of the Hemoben and ceftriaxone mixture was also more pronounced than when using Hemoben alone. Histological examination of the liver in animals receiving the mixture showed fewer inflammatory cells and less pronounced necrotic processes. This indicates a significant anti-inflammatory and antimicrobial effect of the combination of the drugs.

Fig. 3. Comparison of platelet levels in the first and second groups.

When evaluating liver condition after gallbladder removal in animals receiving the Hemoben and ceftriaxone mixture, a decrease in biochemical markers of liver damage was recorded. The average ALT level was 45 ± 5 U/l, which was 30% lower than in the group receiving only Hemoben (65 ± 6 U/l, $p < 0.05$). Similarly, the AST level in the combination group was 50 ± 4 U/l, which was 28% lower compared to the group receiving only Hemoben (69 ± 7 U/l, $p < 0.05$) (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. Comparison of biochemical marker levels in the first and second groups.

This suggests that the mixture had a more pronounced protective effect on the liver, preventing inflammation and liver cell destruction.

Thus, the obtained results demonstrate that the combination of Hemoben and ceftriaxone has more pronounced hemostatic and antimicrobial properties, which may be related to the synergistic mechanism of action of these drugs. Ceftriaxone enhances the antibacterial effect, preventing tissue infection, while Hemoben promotes faster regeneration and coagulation. Therefore, the use of this mixture represents a more effective approach for preventing complications after cholecystectomy, especially in the presence of a risk of infectious complications.

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